

The Importance of Drama in English Language Teaching for Preparatory School Students

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Abstract: The drama lessons were, and still are, suffering from obstacles that holding them back from being taught to students in preparatory schools, and this created a gap that began to widen with time and distance students from this great art. In his teaching, I explained the anticipated objectives of the drama. And I talked about the importance of drama in teaching English language and extent of its impact on the students, too.

In conclusion, with the proposed solutions and the actions that must be followed to employ drama in reality in teaching students. to expand their language vocabulary to present.

Key points: Drama, plays, theatrical texts, educational mechanism.

Introduction

Drama can be beneficial for cross-curricular learning not only in acquiring the English language but also moving up spiritually and culturally in life. Teaching and drama are similar in that they are closely related in the process of learning and engaging with students. The principle of every lesson is that the teacher should, before and during the class, attract students to the lesson, instill a passion for knowledge, break away from routine solutions that create boredom, and spread knowledge. Therefore traditional education can be described as a core curriculum that focuses on the outside of the student. Literary and linguistic activities in the educational process became an important stimulating and influencing factor in the formation and refinement of the scientific and social personality of students, by inculcating a set of principles, skills and positive behaviors. At the forefront of these skills is self-expression, condensing ideas in the head in a clear and unambiguous language.

Drama is considered one of the characteristics of the past centuries and should be studied and read because it represents the historical record of the people who preceded us from the past to the present, as well as their outlook on life and philosophy. The remarkable influence that literature has on the human psyche is due to the fact that it brings everyday language closer to the heart and mind, so it contributes to the improvement of the recipient's mental and intellectual abilities and self-improvement.

When language becomes clear, this clarity in language comes from the use of common words, so they are understandable to the recipient or listener. Aristotle talks about the important concept of cryptic language. This means that the language of the text is rhetorical and there is no slack in the use of unusual words in it. Roman Jakobson described the functions of language: affective, persuasive, descriptive, directive, and poetic. Edward Lee Thorndike believed that the function of language was not only to express one's thoughts and feelings, but also to evoke thoughts and feelings in listeners and readers. This means that there are words that touch and influence the soul, and have their own nature and composition. For this reason, it is said, the words that come out of the heart fall into the heart, and those that come out of the tongue do not go beyond the ears because language is like the body and its spirit is the meaning.

Literature, especially drama, was considered the main source of language teaching and the main object of study in the grammar and translation curriculum. Therefore, learning a language at that time was aimed as learning the play itself, the teacher provided students with literary texts to translate the language being studied into the national language, and the purpose was learning a foreign language. It consisted of reading written plays and benefiting from them in the training and development of intellectual abilities. Some linguists and critics believe that the play represents an example of filling in the missing linguistic context in foreign language education in other countries.

This is because this drama creates a reality and linguistic context that cannot be obtained in countries where the language is not spoken, and this context represents a different world.

Therefore, Integrated language includes practical instructions, language exercises, and language rules that are linked to linguistic knowledge so that the required forms of expression are carried out through written texts or positions of oral or written expression. This leads not only to language practice in terms of listening, speaking, reading, writing and emotional aspects, but also to the attitudes and values that students gain by studying the comprehensive topics of the curriculum through drama.

Definition of Drama and its importance

Drama is considered one of the teaching methods that helps enrich and deepen the educational process for all students due to its connection to the direct experience resulting from the learner's activity and effectiveness. Drama does not focus on the mental process only, but rather takes into account the psychological and social needs of the learner "Drama will also provide a bridge for the students who understand to become their role in sharing responsibilities with their classmates" (Wagner p.227).

Moreover, Drama in English literature is a type of literary work that represents a dialogue between characters and describes narrative events on stage. The drama aims to arouse the emotions and feelings of the audience and introduce them to the various characters, their feelings and thoughts. It has been classified into several types, including comedy, tragedy, social and historical drama, romance, fantasy, and others. Among the most famous English plays are "Hamlet" "Romeo and Juliet" by Shakespeare, "Miss Joliffe" by Oscar Wilde, and "The War of the Worlds" by H.G. Wells. and others are among the most famous theatrical works in history.

Drama is all that the human mind sought to express, whether organized or scattered. There is no doubt about it. Literature is more than just vocabulary and expressions used to teach rules or draw grammatical or rhetorical relationships, as many linguists think. The pleasure and taste of these works of literature, whose sweetness can only be felt by reading them "that the key which unlocks the secret of the mysterious power drama"(P:24 Hornbrook). It is nothing more than written prose or poetry. The collections we are reading are a superficial view and a limited understanding of this great art, and many of us have narrowed our conception of it and limited to easy-to-read books. By limiting ourselves to templates, it slowly began to move away from us, and the truth is that it is the general art that represents the headquarters. It goes without saying how many poems have been sung, how many novels have been written, how many stories have been told, and how many people's hearts and minds have been deeply influenced.

Literature is the soul and living heart of language, and it is no exaggeration to say that a language without literature becomes a lifeless, motionless body. If literature arises in language, life arises in literature in all its manifestations: happiness and misery, death and life, love and hate, honesty and betrayal. It expands the linguistic space of learners, not to mention its important and delicate role in language education, and if you want to summarize the meaning of literature in words, you can say it is national literature that means civilization, development, thought, and history. English drama is an important part of the English literary heritage, as English theatrical works are famous for expressing human feelings and social, political, moral and cultural tendencies in English society. Elements of drama in English literature include the following:

- 1- Dialogue: where events are communicated through dialogue between characters.

- 2- Events: These are the events that converge and intertwine to produce the complete story.
- 3- Characters: They are the main people in the events and those who carry them out.
- 4- Rhythm: It is the formula used to organize drama and distribute it in time.
- 5- Theatrical atmosphere: It is the atmosphere that is created for the audience to make attachment to the events and live them by interacting with the characters.

Drama and Language

Language teaching is currently based on dividing the material into branches such as: For example, there are disciplines such as grammar, morphology, reading and writing, and if these disciplines are unified, integrated and interconnected, and each discipline is presented to students in an integrated manner, it is useless to differentiate between these disciplines. Dictation education is not just proper reading, especially in reading lessons, but a language system in which each area of the language complements each other, reaches the learner appropriately and accurately, and allows them to enjoy and perform the language to the fullest.

The function of language is communication, and it is known that among the functions of language is a dialogue function that confirms social communication between members of society. The functions of language also include the imaginative functions of language, which lead to creative ideas that represent creative uses of language, such as writing stories or writing novels.

The language of drama and plays

The linguistic style used in the language of plays is the narrative style in which the speaker tries to appear the essence of the speech in the most beautiful way possible. For example, there may be a sentence or word that has no meaning or it is an ordinary sentence that does not carry any effect that would move the listener's feelings. Therefore, the speaker in dramatic plays tries to change their meanings to make them seem deeper and more meaningful.

However, the language of dramatic plays is an integrated dialogue that is used to give an artistic and dramatic character to the dialogue. Dramatic theatrical dialogue is also used in a wonderful linguistic way, and although the language used is colloquial, grammar and vocabulary are used in an optimal way. For example, a person who wants to learn the language is advised to read Shakespeare's books and plays; This is because it is a complete linguistic guide that will give you the opportunity to understand the English language and culture in a wonderful way.

How do English teachers use language with drama subject?

If the teacher is explaining a novel or play to students and wants to use the Role-Play strategy, he must do the following:

He identifies specific scenes or parts of the play or novel, and then students choose who will present. They are asked to memorize and understand the theatrical scenes well and practice them well. Be dressed in costumes if the appropriate costume is available to embody the characters of the play so that they are more realistic. The teacher monitors the students' performance and how they use the English language with correct pronunciation and form. "When engaging in drama, students draw on their knowledge of social conversations and behavior"(P:17 Manfred), that is embodied in the text to express their activities in their daily lives.

Benefits of Role-Play for Students

Building students' confidence, especially when speaking English

Exchange of information between students

Learning through groups

Develop a high EQ [Emotional quotient]

Benefits of Role-Play for English language teachers

English becomes easy to learn for students to use in many situations.

It saves teachers time and effort in the classroom by using active teaching methods.

Develop a better understanding of the student mind and a better comprehension of asked questions

It helps teachers know the extent to which students comprehend the information provided by the teacher "Drama demands enthusiasm - not only for the lesson, but also for the students" (P:15 Wessels) Provides a fun and effective learning environment at the same time.

The role of drama and its impact on education

Drama is considered a recreational function because it makes the student more capable of learning, "it would seem that drama is more powerful than any other medium in education" (Wagner p.227) develops a sense for the furthermore beauty of art, thus increases the student's imagination, which may lead to creativity, strengthen self-confidence, and enriches information for the student, by expanding his awareness, ridding the student of repression and excessive emotions, and helping him to getting rid of speech defects, increasing his knowledge, developing his ability to express fluently, and influencing his speech. The behavior of others through persuasion, and modifying the student's behavior because of the guidance it includes general.

1. It enriches the individual's ability to express what is inside him to become more capable of influencing and directing others. In order to meet his needs and solve his problems.
2. It provides the opportunity for a person to experience different life situations where he develops solutions for them and tries to adapt to them.
3. A person gets to know others by examining their personalities and becomes more able to deal with them
4. A person gets to know himself, his abilities and talents, which helps him develop his personality.
5. It tames the body and develops the senses through rhythmic dance, dramatic play, and expression
6. It gives the individual self-confidence and strengthens the bond of friendship with adults, which helps him learn.
7. It increases the individual's information and satisfies his curiosity.
8. Simplifies academic subjects by dramatizing them in a bright and attractive manner.
9. It enriches the individual's language, eliminates speech defects, and modifies behavior.
10. Prepares children for adult drama.
11. It gives strength, courage and wisdom.

The field of the educational process has been and is still under research and development to find the most successful methods. The most vibrant of them, to make the teaching method inside and outside the classroom more dynamic. It is easy to help the recipient student understand the educational material, develop his personality, and give him abilities. Honest and easy skills and knowledge that are relevant to his environment and daily life, and drama is one of the approaches to teaching. Which helps enrich and deepen the learning process for all ages and all grades, due to its connection to experience. Direct resulting from the activity and effectiveness of the learner.

Objectives of drama in the educational process

Educational drama makes the student the basis and focus of the educational process as he discovers information by himself, this method makes the student alert and active throughout the educational time, in addition to that drama connects Theoretical and practical aspects. "Drama in schools has also been marked by reluctance to engage with process of skill acquisition" (P:5 Hornbrook). One

of the goals that educational drama seeks to achieve in the educational process, within educational institutions, which educators have called for the need to pay attention to, are as follows:

1. Develop the ability to solve problems and make decisions through improvisation, discussions, and role-playing.
2. Transforming academic curricula, especially those that are difficult and dry in style, into relevant attitudes and experiences meaning that the learner can understand easily and in a way that is pleasing to the soul.
3. Developing the artistic taste among learners through a sense of the beauty of what is involved in theatrical work. From multiple arts in the art of linguistic, motor performance and musical formation. "Of course, dramatic texts reach a socially more widespread audience through the media of film and television"(P:34 Pfister)
4. Refine students' talents by revealing their diverse abilities and working to develop and direct them. Such as speech, acting, drawing, interior design, management, direction, and others capabilities
5. Improving and diversifying the teaching methods used, and moving away from traditional ones.
6. Linking curricula to different life matters, and developing the student's awareness and understanding of the society around him. "The link between drama and other curricular activities can be dynamic and not merely a passive means to convenient follow up activities" [P:17 O'Neill].
7. Affirming the child's self and eliminating shyness.
8. Encouraging organized group work.
9. Helping the student to develop some positive attitudes, such as cooperation, belonging, and fair competition.. This is done by presenting him in different roles and experiencing the situations that he represents or witnesses
10. Addressing some behavioral problems among participants, identifying participants' feelings, and increasing their self-confidence.
11. Strengthening the relationship between teacher and student, and enhancing meanings of identity and social ties.
12. Helping students learn through the environment and developing their imagination.

Elements of a dramatic text

The dramatic elements contribute to the nature and degree of the effect to be achieved. Different values, including multiple values. There is no doubt that any dramatic text, whether educational, theatrical or radio, must contain a number of the elements that form its general, aesthetic, emotional, and intellectual, so these elements must be given importance: the idea, the plot, the character, the dialogue, and the general psychological atmosphere.

First: the idea

The idea constitutes the stable depth in the dramatic text, and it is like a pearl buried in the depths of the sea. Despite the movement and rush of the sea, it remains centered, much like a growing organism. Gradually, it is shaped and influenced by the circumstances surrounding it, and the idea is a moving energy that is manifested in every detail of the text and its elements

Second: the plot

One of the elements of the text, and it is more hidden in the dramatic text, as it remains hidden and concealed and does not It can only be perceived mentally, despite its vitality and influence on all elements, and it is as he described it. Aristotle represents the soul from the body.

Third: Personality

Personality is the basis that carries the characteristics of the dramatic world, and the characters are diverse and different, so personality. Drama establishes its effectiveness through the surrounding circumstances, and it is one voice, while the text contains number of characters.

Fourth: Dialogue

Dialogue is the clear element in the text, and it forms the basis of the text, especially in drama. Educational, and the functions of dialogue include: developing the story, event, character, atmosphere, and situation, as it contributes. By drawing the recipient to the text by describing the dialogue, it is the link between the dramatic character and the recipient.

Fifth: The solution

The solution is considered the final scene in which things that remained unknown appear and the complex issues that were previously resolved, "the scene presents the situation to the audience in such a light with values, felt through the stage, that enlarge the meaning of the last act"(P:39 Styan) meaning that the solution must be reasonable, clear, and appropriate to the events and capabilities of the recipient. "audience meets the characters. Here, the author brings dominant ideas announcing the themes of the text. In complication, problems or mysteries, which have to be solved, test for the character's action and movement".(p;8 Jasim). It should be happy, spread joy and a spirit of optimism, and the solution should be logical, so that: The event progresses from the node to the solution.

Obstacles to dramatic activity

There are obstacles that affect the use of dramatic activity in schools, and the most important of these obstacles are:

1. Lack of interest in in-service teacher training programs to train them on the skills of using patterns different dramas, and the skills of drafting dramatic content.
2. Discouraging some educational leaders, whether at the school administration level or at the guidance level technical support for teachers to implement acting activities, because they are not convinced of their educational importance.
3. Scarcity of specialized teachers and prepared academically and professionally in drama. "New educators agree that continuity is very important and that if all teachers are trained to use drama this would help to safeguard the student's opportunity for dramatic experience in schools". [p.128 Dodd]
4. The large number of burdens placed on the teacher, which is represented by the large number of classes he teaches, In addition to the administrative work assigned to him by the school administration, which makes him finally find difficulty in providing the time necessary to apply drama in teaching.
5. An increase in the number of students in the classroom, in addition to its narrow space, as this does not provide an opportunity for the teacher, for dramatic application, due to the difficulties he faces.
6. Lack of financial allocations necessary to spend on dramatic activities.

How to reduce obstacles to school dramatic activity

A good teacher is one who works as much as possible to overcome these difficulties with some effort. Flexibility and perseverance, because the fruits of learning that can be gained from applying drama are many and varied. It is worth making every effort for it, from every teacher who is loving and dedicated to his work, and a believer at the same time. The importance and seriousness of the role that the teacher can play, to graduate new generations capable of achieving excellence. Obstacles to dramatic activity can be reduced through:

1. Linking school activities, especially the school curriculum, to real life, through declared educational goals. It takes place both inside the classroom, and through the practice of dramatic school activities.
2. Providing theatrical texts appropriate for each educational stage, and organizing theatrical composition courses.
3. Establishing school theaters in modern schools.
4. Providing booklets accompanying the school curriculum, which include school plays that serve the courses. Study books, so that the textbook includes mentions of them and the names of their authors, creators, and availability. In school libraries, to be read in free reading classes, under the supervision and follow-up of the teacher.
5. Reducing the burden placed on the teacher by reducing the number of classes and reducing administrative burdens.
6. Reducing the number of students within one class, and distributing them into study groups, so that the teacher can perform his role, and use drama successfully.
7. Allocate a special budget for this type of education, to spend on dramatic activities.

Importance of Stories and Novels in Language Teaching

The process of teaching languages, including English, should enhance language skills such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing in order to develop and improve learners' language abilities. That's certainly the purpose. In this context, the growing enthusiasm for language learning among foreign learners has led, on the one hand, to the development of pedagogies and methods to be continuously adopted in language teaching, so that the educational process meets this urgent demand. It presents a good opportunity to take action. It aims at learning, and secondly, it is also done in a simple and smooth way that meets the learners' expectations of learning the language and fulfilling their desires from the language. Therefore, the process of investing a story and making it serve the educational goals of the language is a particular pattern in the development of teaching methods and techniques, as it involves many educational mechanisms, the most prominent of which are as follows: It presents a living language in various educational situations and plays an important role in awakening the learners and making them learn based on the tension that the language relies on in presenting the events and facts in the story. "When engaging in drama, 'students' draw on their knowledge of social conventions and behavior" (P:17 Fleming).

Therefore, stories contain a large amount of linguistic data that is generally beneficial to the language learner's learning process, and furthermore, they provide a qualitative supplement in teaching various elements of language, including structure and vocabulary. It is considered an important educational resource. which allows you to climb the ladder of different levels of language proficiency. In addition to the use of stories and their incorporation into the language teaching process, many pedagogical aspects are necessary. The most important of which is that it helps learners develop phonological and linguistic awareness, and also helps them understand phonetic distinctions and language differences. Moreover, it helps them achieve fluency and speed in reading and improve reading comprehension, thus developing reading comprehension skills, which leads to their attraction and maintaining the linguistic balance and important vocabulary. It can be used again to compose written and oral dialogue.

In general, stories are particularly important in education because they help learners improve their language skills and also provide them with the vocabulary and expressions they need to speak in different languages and communicate successfully in situations with different communication topics.

What importance does it, a dismissed subject, have for students?

Drama acts as an outlet for all the wonderful thoughts in every person's head; they are handed the script for the play, or the character they were assigned and then it is their job to blow life into it on

the stage, all the while being guided by the script. Every person who acts the character out will bring a special, different kind of spice, allowing them to express themselves fully. This is creativity.

As for the script, think of it like the lines in a students' coloring book; they are free to do whatever their heart desires as long as it is inside the lines. All of this challenges the student to open their minds to all the ideas circling around the earth, to use their minds and bodies to show what they learned from a piece of text and paper and finally to tell a story in whatever way they desire; the options on stage are endless— words, song, mime, puppetry, playwriting...the list goes on and on. Another important thing students learn from drama and theatre, which is crucial for developing skills they need in the future: confidence.

Students who study drama, or who perform on a stage for an audience, need to possess a special kind of self-confidence, thus enhancing their ability to portray the given character as freely as possible. "An improved sense of confidence in the student in his or her ability to learn the target language"(P:13 Wessels). Low self-confidence is more often associated with a tendency to evade being the center of attention and quietness of speech in addition to being physically uncomfortable with yourself, which surely affects the student's ability to communicate and interact with other humans.

In addition to affecting the mental image he has of himself, there will be many changes that occur to him, without he even noticing, when he performs on a stage. The way he talk, the way he hold himself, even his acceptance to doing things he wouldn't usually go for before, all change due to theatre. Student can perform for dozens of people by the guidance of just a paper of lines, (which wouldn't even be with him in the performance, for information) but he can't talk to the cashier at the grocery shop without stuttering, surely not. The stage teaches him how to move the world, and this is the only one in for him, and how to perform is just shoulders back, hold his head high, forgetting everything around him , all of this in their daily lives.

Communication is perhaps the most important 21st century skill students can learn in the drama classroom. Humans communicate with each other in the real world every day, in many ways: verbally, nonverbally, physically, "such cases, the dramatic text undermines the horizon of expectation of the contemporary audience or readers by implementing"(P:31 Pfister). They often have to navigate the place of miscommunication through mixed messages or people who refuse to listen, which makes this endeavor to be even more difficult.

Communication is important to a successful theatrical experience. The play is a two-way street, what is sent from the stage receives an immediate response from the audience. To pull off a successful performance, all the participants need to be in tune with each other, for the play to run as smooth as possible. They need to be able to communicate with each other, discreetly, while being on stage, in addition to communicating the idea they wish to convey to the audience. Participating in drama teaches young and old people alike exactly how to do that and, over time, this will begin to leak into their daily lives too; it will affect how they try to make their ideas known to other people. Theatre exposes people to new ways of communicating with fresh vocabulary – through the arts of dance, acting and music. Furthermore, theatre enhances their ability to work as a team united for a certain goal, like the success of a play or winning a group award, which also is reflected in their day to day life.

Looking at the big picture (or you could say how parents would see it), theatre doesn't seem to have the largest impact on our lives, or so we think. When taught in an enjoyable, correct way, drama adds so much to so many aspects of our lives, without us even realizing it. It strengthens skills we use every day, for the rest of our lives and it builds a person's personality in ways that math never could.

The influence of English drama on English literature

English drama is a performing art consisting of certain stories and events acted out on stage to convey a certain message to the audience. English drama is considered one of the most influential

representational art forms in English literature. The development of English drama began in the late Middle Ages, and has constantly evolved into what it is today.

Shakespeare is considered one of the largest and most famous authors in the history of English drama, as he presented many famous works such as Macbeth, Richard III, and Hamlet. English drama also presented many other famous works, such as the play “Capital” by Marx and “Pearl” by the unknown English writer.

English drama is an important source of English literature, as it reflects a variety of issues, feelings and ideas that have been important to English societies over the years "The dramatist has always conceived embodied human relationships rather than a design of words like a poem."(P:50 By J. L. Styan) which it reflects the feelings inside a person that are expressed in words.

Drama in the Iraqi curriculum for fifth grade

The drama that students deal with in the curriculum talks about what drama is It is a mode of fiction in which a written text is intended to be performed for an audience by actors on a stage, through dialogue and series of events that depict human life, conflicts and emotions and the origin of the word drama "comes from the Greek word for action"(P:115 Johnston). The elements of drama are director, actors, theatre and audience and types of drama tragedy and comedy and it is influenced by the types of drama that come from the Greeks, the Romans and the Renaissance dramatists. Drama entered Iraq only in the late nineteenth century, where it was taught in Iraqi schools to give a moral lesson. Then in 1920s it became general and dealt with Arab history and their courage, but the drama movement remained weak in Iraq due to the lack of theaters and the lack of professional directors and actors.

The importance of Drama cannot be truly shown without a curriculum. Drama will be something great again by change – the day the education system pays mind to such an important subject.. Until then, we are pretty much powerless to the current curriculum. But the prospect of change actually occurring is not completely out of the question.

The visual arts did not flourish much until the early twentieth century, but in the 1930s and 1940s, the Ministry of Culture sent a number of gifted local artists to study in Europe. Upon their return, these artists instilled contemporary aesthetics like impressionism in the community. By starting studios, offering art instruction, setting up artists' collectives and exhibitions, they shared their experiences and expertise in the field of painting. The majority of these artists were modernist teachers. Additionally, they deliberately looked for a visual language that would combine Iraqi themes and customs with modern abstract art. These artists served as the core of the founding group and the initial faculty members of the College of Fine Arts. and that was the first time drama was introduced in Iraq.

The drama and theater movement increased in strength when the Institute of Fine Arts was established in Baghdad , and when Haqqi Al-Shibli appeared in 1945. The curriculum has two works, one of which was Jawad al-Asadi, an Iraqi actor and director. Among his most important works are *Women in War* and *The Baghdadi Bath*. *The Baghdadi Bath*, which deals with the difficulty of life, especially the period between the American occupation and the former regime and the devastation it caused in the lives of Iraqis. It is a thoughtful picture of the everyday horror of surviving in a war zone. The drama, *Baghdadi Bath*, showed a continuous argument between the two brothers over money, which ended their lives in a tragic end, as they were victims of harsh condition.

The other work, it was about the well-known writer Shakespeare, and it had one of Shakespeare’s works, which is the play *The Tempest*. There was a conflict between the two characters in the play Caliban and Prospero. The fact that a major motif in this play is that Caliban is an island native, while the other characters are colonizers. Caliban is a unique character and he has many different personalities. He lives in the island alongside the protagonist, Prospero and his daughter Miranda. We can say that Caliban is the only character in the play who is truly native to this land. However,

Prospero used his magic in order to control Caliban and force him to act as his servant. Caliban resents Prospero for enslaving him and stealing his land.

As a result, all these events are lessons that learn the students a language and a moral lesson that helps them face difficulties of life and solve their problems easily.

These are some pictures of fifth-grade preparatory students performing plays inspired by the novels of our choice in the class.

Conclusion

The importance of drama can be summarized in the human tendency towards beauty, as literature in general is based on sensual and emotional concepts that can transport the reader into a vast world of imagination. Therefore, the purpose of literature is to develop students' literary sense, expand their linguistic richness, make them aware of the culture of that language, and develop their artistic skills to analyze, criticize and extract literary texts and images from it and to develop their creative expression. Note that it is about enabling. And projecting it onto their culture and other cultures, this goal moves forward to become what it should be, with teachers following an integrated approach and practical steps to the reality of teaching literature that it can only be achieved by letting others do so, and that it can be achieved accordingly. We must: Develop and change strategies for teaching literature.

There is a need to create a new literature curriculum that takes into account the integration of aspects of literature education. Introducing modern technology into literature education classrooms. Developing teachers themselves and their abilities according to the demands of the new generation. Not to mention considering the prescribed curriculum and the number of hours allotted to it, as well as the appropriate way to present it, will enhance the spirit of creativity in the students and break down the walls of imitation. Teachers must take care of their own training and development in order to acquire a level of knowledge of techniques and technology that allows them to transfer from ancient methods to modern methods and apply them to the study of drama.

Encourage students to express their opinions artistically and objectively in the text presented, projecting project the text on their own culture and literature and the literature of the peoples they know by mentioning the similarities and differences between cultures. Assign students to analyze a text, critique it, compare it to other texts, and focus on students' understanding and use of new figurative meanings. Encourage students to memorize some literary texts and encourage new writers to further pursue by projecting literary texts into activities such as plays, poetry forums, literary programs, press interviews, radio reports, etc. We encourage you to study the works of and publisher author. Not all students are good at studying literature, so teachers can engage with students and encourage them to read international stories and appreciate translated works, providing them with extra-curricular pleasures.

References

1. Betti, Mohammed Jasim (2015). An Introduction to Drama UNIVERSITY OF THIQRAR.
2. Dodd,N. and W. Hickson.(1977). Drama and Theatre in Education. London: Heinemann.

3. Fleming, Mike (2011). *Starting Drama Teaching*. Taylor & Francis.
4. Finlay-Johnson, Harriet(2018). *The Dramatic Method of Teaching*. Boston U.S.A.
5. Hornbrook, David (2002). *Education In Drama*. London: Routledge.
6. Johnston, Olivia and Farrell, Mark (2018). *English for Iraq*. UK: Garnet Education.
7. O'Neill, C. and A. Lambert.(1989). *Drama Structures. A Practical Handbook for Teachers*. London: Hutchinson.
8. Pfister, Manfred (1993). *The Theory and Analysis of Drama*. Cambridge University.
9. Styan, J. L. (2001). *The Elements of Drama*. Cambridge University.
10. Wagner, B.(1989). *Dorothy Heatcote: Drama as a Learning Medium*. London: Hutchinson.
11. Wessels, Charlyn (2003). *Drama*. Oxford University.